

**MODERN RIETER C60 CARD COMBING MACHINES HEAD DRUM
UNIT COMBING PROCESS IMPROVEMENT**

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Abstract. The article describes the improvement of the combing process of the head drum of the modern rieter c60 card combing machines in order to eliminate uneven ribbons, reduce yarn breaks and defects, and improve the quality of the yarn in spinning factories, and analyzes the working bodies and mechanisms of the carding machines, justifying the technical parameters and operating modes.

Key words: Carding machines, mechanism, uneven tapes, yarn, cotton fibers, spinning mill, fabric.

At present, the main goal in Uzbekistan is to increase the material, cultural and spiritual standard of living of the population, building an economy based on free market relations. This means a decent and prosperous life for our people, taking a worthy place in the international arena. Today, in a period of rapid development in our country, no industry should be left behind. The republic is implementing comprehensive measures aimed at organizing the production of a wide range of high-quality textiles and garments and knitwear, deepening the localization of its production, as well as increasing the export potential of local producers. In particular, textile and light industry enterprises are rapidly developing every day. In recent years, the result of political and social changes in our country has had a positive impact on this sector as well [1].

CARDING:The carding is the second process of spinning which converts fed material (lap) into the uniform strand of fibres called "sliver". The good quality carding of cotton is very important because the yarn quality very much depends upon it. The neps percentage in the yarn varies according to the quality of carding process. "The carding is called the heart of spinning". In the carding process, the material gets passed through a carding machine. The fibres are made parallel to each other. The fibers tangle in this operation, thus it makes it possible to remove all types of impurities present in the cotton.

The carding, stripping and raising action take place during carding operation. In this way, a continuous uniform sliver having a parallel fibre arrangement almost free of impurities is obtained after carding process [2].

Fig.1. Schematic diagram of carding machine

The research work carried out on the CHMS-450 machine, which is pulled with TSMPL-7 set (Fig. 2.a), with two rollers with a diameter of 60 mm, allows to draw a number of conclusions. Installing a pair of rollers in the front part of the hats on the machine naturally improves the quality of combing, reduces the amount of threads coming out of the hats, the unevenness of the braid and yarn, and increases the relative strength of the yarn. When the use of rollers increases the working efficiency of the carding machine, the deterioration of the pile quality indicators allows compensation. When the rollers are installed, the number of hats in the working part of the machine can be reduced. In many modern hat combing machines, additional combing segments or fixed hats are installed in the area of the hat canvas. (picture-2.b) Combing segments improve the process of combing and leveling [3]. Increasing the speed of the hat canvas leads to a decrease in the impurities of the combed pile. The amount of hat pulls is proportional to the hat movement speed. Compared to the elastic garnet, the use of a semi-rigid garnet reduces the number of hatted garnets by 1.41% without reducing the quality of the garnet, while keeping many dirty and short fibers.

Theoretical analysis and conducted experiments show that for the performance of hat canvas, the needles of the set should have a slope angle, the height of the tooth is from 0.2 to 2.3 mm, the set number is reduced to 80. I.V. Chkhaidze [4] shows that the possibility of long fibers passing from the hats to the drum is more in the back rows of the needle (depending on the movement) than in the front. This means that the needles in the hats take up and comb the fiber material more actively than in front of the back rows. Therefore, the author suggests reducing the working width of the hat or creating a space above the hat to increase the probability of passing long fibers from the hats to the head drum.

Fig.2. The main part of the drum

Therefore, it is recommended to use a cleaned surface to create an active combing zone with a reduction of the hat surface: a second hat surface, combing segments or other working bodies.

There are wide opinions about the participation of hats in the leveling movements of combing machines. So, in general, D. Kaufman [5] believed that the effect of flattening hats can be neglected, but I.G. After conducting experimental research, Borzunov showed that the percentage of caps in the process of leveling is 50-76%.

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